

WG6 Workshop “Citizen Science in Social Sciences and Humanities”

Date: 07/08-03-2018

Participants (signed via e-COST): Katrin Vohland, Egle Butkeviciene, Maria Begoña Peña Lang, Anna Cigarini, Loreta Tauginiene, Manuel Portela, Egle Vaidelyte, Vaidas Morkevicius, Dario Martinelli.

Other participants (including via Skype): Aiste Balzekiene, Monika Suškevičs, Maria Daskolia, Katja Mayer.

Hosts: Kaunas University of Technology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities (Kaunas, Lithuania)

Programme:

Wednesday, March 7

13:00 – 15:00 Workshop

Welcome speech / Logistics / Aims and plans for this workshop (Egle Butkeviciene)

Introductory speech: a short presentation on a topic (Katrin Vohland)

Introducing our experience to each other: short introductions of workshop participants and their short presentations about the experience regarding CS initiatives, examples, or any other aspects of CS in SSH, including previous projects and literature analysis/reviews (5 min each)

15:30 – 17:30 Workshop

Working on a concept: “What are the issues/ topics CS in SSH is focussed on?”

Concept mapping activities & discussions (Design thinking Lab)

Possible outcome: case identification for further analysis (with possibilities to develop some cases for the article). Moderator: Dario Martinelli & Egle Butkeviciene

Thursday, March 8

08:30 – 10:00 Workshop

Working on a method: “What are the methods CS in SSH is using?”

A presentation on methods in SSH (Vaidas Morkevicius)

Discussions and activities to identify methods (as well as validity, reliability issues, ethics) of CS in SSH

(Design thinking Lab). Possible outcome: case identification for further analysis (with possibilities to develop some cases for the article). Moderator: Vaidas Morkevicius

10:30 – 12:00 Workshop

Finalizing the workshop: summary, aims achieved, further plans

Summary of the workshop:

In this workshop, we aimed at mapping the opportunities and challenges for Citizen Science in Social Sciences and Humanities. This workshop focused on discussing the concept, methods and existing practices of citizen science in SSH, such as through action research methodology and the use of citizens as volunteers to track their behaviors and perceptions in everyday life. To improve our understanding of citizen science in SSH the workshop set a target to develop a paper as an outcome of this COST activity.

Decisions:

1. Develop an article (Google docs)
2. Timetable:
 - a. Minutes, pictures, + Dropbox – by 03/16
 - b. First ideas by 1st May (in Google docs)
 - c. First ideas drafted by 5th June (to be discussed during the MC meeting in Geneva)
 - d. Second draft by 30th August 2018.
3. Authorship:
 - a. Each who contributes substantially (for example, draft an additional paragraph or section) should be nominated as author defining clearly the responsibility of each author, for example, pages or topics covered could be defined. In case of data collection, it should be agreed in advance on the process of drafting the work between the research leader and others. Rewording, commenting and correction of typing and/or grammar errors are not considered as substantial contribution, i.e. they are not a part of authorship credit, but might be treated as contribution to be acknowledged. In all other cases such as technical assistance (for example, search of journals for publication) should be treated as contributors defining clearly the role of each contributor.
 - b. Authors' Identification: who is contributing to the article as authors (**please confirm your intention by e-mail!**)
4. Literature review: copy articles to Dropbox folder "Literature". To avoid duplications, please name articles "YEAR_Name_of_the_Author" (e. g. 2017_Estel_et_al)
5. Cases: title and keywords
6. Structure of the article:
 - a. Introduction
 - b. Historical context
 - c. Methodology -> make a table of keywords and databases *a priori*
 - d. Evolution of citizens' involvement in science (different disciplines – EU classification, 8-10 case per discipline):
 - i. Methods used (& changes over time: reliability aspects, types of data, etc. ...)
 - ii. Role of scientists & citizens
 - e. Comparative analysis of citizen involvement in different research fields (mapping, tables, network analysis...)
 - f. Discussion and conclusions
7. Initial distribution of tasks:
 - a. Methodological part: Vaidas & Maria Begona
 - b. Natural sciences: Katrin
 - c. Engineering: Maria Begona
 - d. Humanities and arts: Dario
 - e. Social sciences:
 - i. Management – Loreta, Maria Begona
 - ii. Sociology and political sciences – Egle B., Egle V., Vaidas, Anna;
 - iii. Human geography - Manuel

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

Workshop Report

Pictures:

The poster features logos for ktu (socialinių, humanitarinių mokslų ir menų fakultetas) and ktu 100 Atkurtai Lietuvai. The main title is ECOST-MEETING-CA15212-070318-093675. Below it, the workshop title is 'Workshop: Mapping Opportunities and Challenges for Citizen Science in Social Sciences and Humanities' with the date 2018-03-07/08. A paragraph describes the workshop's focus on citizen science in SSH, research methodology, and citizen participation. At the bottom, it states 'A Framework in Science and Technology to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe.' and 'COST is supported by the EU Framework Programme Horizon 2020'.

